

MANAGING SCHOOLS THROUGH THE LENS OF GAY ADMINISTRATORS

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Managing Schools through the Lens of Gay Administrators

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ABSTRACT

This study digs into the experiences and challenges faced by gay school leaders in Baybay City, Employing Hermeneutic Phenomenological qualitative study as research design. The participants of this study were two (2) gay school administrators in Baybay City Schools Division. Results uncovered five main themes in their stories: Evolution of Experiences, Challenges and Resilience, Best Practices and Success Stories, Harmony in Leadership, and Diversity and Inclusive Leadership. Moreover, the study shows that gay administrators have diverse experiences but share a strong commitment to education. Resilience is crucial for effective school management, helping personal growth, and building a tough educational community. Collaborative leadership styles are crucial in creating a positive school culture. Furthermore, the study wraps up by recognizing gay administrators as promoters of inclusivity, significantly impacting the creation of a welcoming educational environment. Therefore, it is recommended to include designing programs for their unique challenges, supporting their advocacy for inclusive policies, and fostering community engagement. Also, the study adds a valuable layer to the understanding of school leadership and suggests practical ways to create more inclusive, resilient, and harmonious schools. It also recommends to call for ongoing support and recognition of the diverse contributions of gay administrators in education.

Keywords: *gay administration, LGBTQA+, gay leadership in School*

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been an increasing awareness of the need for diversity and inclusivity in educational settings, particularly regarding the Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer (LGBTQ+) community. Despite significant progress in achieving equality for LGBTQ+ individuals in various aspects of society, educational institutions continue to face challenges in promoting a safe and supportive environment for these individuals (Hsieh, 2016).

The role of school administrators is critical in ensuring that educational institutions provide a supportive and inclusive environment for all students regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity. However, there is limited research on the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools, and how their experiences inform their leadership practices (Callaghan & Mizzi, 2015; Payne & Smith, 2018). This study addressed the gap in the literature by examining the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools, including the challenges they face, the strategies they use to overcome these challenges, and the impact of their leadership practices on the school community. As administration and leadership are crucial to lead the organization. It is observed that in today's era, LGBTQ+ members play a major role and contribution for the development of the society and the community (Goodhand, 2014; Stargell et al., 2020). There's a lot of issues and concerns in regards to the administration capacity of the members that belong to the LGBTQ+ community such as addressing concerns of the students, leadership, contribution and participation to various activities. Leadership style of gay administrators is in the forefront of criticism and judgement (Bongco & David, 2020; Callaghan & Mizzi, 2015).

This study seeks to contribute to the broader conversation on diversity and inclusion in educational leadership. Understanding the experiences of gay administrators can inform efforts to create more inclusive and equitable educational environments where both students as well as staff members can live happily and grow healthily. Drawing attention to the perspectives and experiences of gay administrators, the study seeks to promote more inclusive educational environments.

To attain the aforementioned objective of this study, I employed a qualitative research approach, incorporating semi-structured interviews with gay administrators across diverse educational settings. The collected data was scrutinized through thematic analysis to discern prevalent themes and patterns in the participants' experiences and perspectives.

The findings of this study have significant implications for educational policy and practice, as they inform efforts to create more inclusive and supportive educational environments for LGBTQ+ students, staff, and administrators. This study has also contributed to the broader literature on diversity and inclusion in educational leadership by highlighting the importance of incorporating the perspectives and experiences of underrepresented groups in leadership research and practice.

Overall, this study sought to provide a deeper understanding of the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools and how these experiences inform their leadership practices. Through this study, it aimed to contribute to the ongoing efforts to promote diversity, equity, and inclusion in educational settings, particularly for the LGBTQ+ community.

Research Questions

The study answers the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools?
2. What meaning can be ascribed from these experiences?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research is qualitative research that used a hermeneutic phenomenological approach by Heidegger (2011). Hermeneutic phenomenology is a qualitative research approach that seeks to understand the meaning and essence of human experiences. This approach is particularly useful for studying complex and multi-layered phenomena, such as the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools. This approach involved collecting data through in-depth interviews with gay administrators, as well as observations and document analysis. The data would be analyzed through a process of bracketing, immersion, description, and interpretation, in order to gain a deep understanding of the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools. It involves a recursive process of interpretation, in which seeks to understand the meaning and essence of the experiences of participants. This process involves a series of steps, including bracketing, immersion, description, and interpretation (Laverty, 2003) and (Zimmerman, 2003).

The Sample and Locale of the Study

The participant selection process for this study was conducted systematically and deliberately to ensure that individuals who met the specific inclusion criteria were included. To be eligible for participation, individuals had to self-identify as gay administrators, signifying their sexual orientation, and currently hold administrative positions within the schools under the Baybay City Division. The study focused on active administrators in the Baybay City Leyte School Division to ensure relevance and contemporaneity of the data collected. Specifically, the participants were Head Teachers or School Principals, who played crucial leadership roles in the school administration. Additionally, previous school heads who have served in their positions for at least 3-5 years are also included in the study to provide valuable insights into the experiences of long-term gay administrators. By meticulously adhering to these inclusion criteria, the study aims to gather comprehensive and relevant data from individuals who possess the necessary experiences and perspectives as gay administrators in the Baybay City Division.

Research Instrument

In this study, interview schedule was the primary instrument used to collect data from the gay administrators. The semi-structured interview allowed for a flexible yet guided conversation that explored the participants' experiences, perspectives, and insights. The interview was

guided by a set of critical questions, focusing on topics related to managing schools as a gay administrator in the Baybay City Division.

The use of a semi-structured interview provided an opportunity for participants to share their thoughts, feelings, and beliefs about their experiences openly and in-depth (Ozaki, 2021). I followed the interview schedule but also have the flexibility to ask follow-up questions and probes deeper into specific areas of interest. This approach allows for a rich exploration of the participants' experiences and allows for a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon being studied.

Audio-video recording devices or mobile phone devices were utilized during the interviews to ensure accuracy and thoroughness in data collection. These devices enabled the researcher to accurately capture the participants' responses and non-verbal cues. Additionally, field notes complemented the audio-video recordings, providing a comprehensive record of the context, observations, and reflections during the interviews. The purpose of using these instruments was to gather comprehensive and detailed data that facilitated a thorough analysis of the experiences, challenges, and strategies employed by gay administrators in managing schools in the Baybay City Division. The semi-structured interview allows for a personalized and participant-centered approach, enabling the participants to share their unique perspectives and insights. The audio-video recordings and field notes served as important documentation to ensure accuracy and enable thorough analysis during the data analysis phase.

Data Gathering

Various data sources were employed to gather information from research participants during the data collection. Some data sources were in-depth interviews with study participants, focus-group discussions, and audio-video recordings.

Preliminary Activities

The data collection procedure for this study involved a systematic and detailed approach to ensure ethical standards were observed and participants' rights were protected.

Firstly, I crafted the transmittal letters and sent to the relevant parties, including a letter to the Dean of the FCIC Graduate School requesting permission to conduct the study and a letter to the school division Superintendent of the target setting seeking authorization. These letters served as formal notifications and established the necessary approvals for the research.

Next, I arranged a meeting with the participants to give them a comprehensive understanding of the study. During the meeting, the purpose and nature of the research were explained, and the informed consent process took place. Participants were given detailed information about the research objectives, procedures, and any potential risks and benefits associated with their participation. Emphasis was placed on ethical standards, such as consent and confidentiality. Participants could ask questions, seek clarification, and make an informed decision about their involvement.

To ensure the comfort and privacy of the participants, I conducted the interviews in a location of their choice. Depending on their preference, this includes their classrooms, offices, or even in FCIC College Faculty Office. The selected location was quiet and conducive to open and

honest discussions. Creating a safe and supportive environment where participants felt at ease sharing their experiences was important.

Confidentiality was a paramount consideration throughout the data collection process. Participants were assured that their identities would remain anonymous and that their personal information would be treated with the utmost confidentiality. A coding system labeled data, ensuring that identifying information was removed or replaced with pseudonyms. This protected the privacy of participants and maintained the confidentiality of their responses. With participants' consent, the interviews were audio-video recorded to capture accurate data. Participants were informed that the recordings will be used solely for research purposes and will be securely stored. They were reassured that the recordings are only accessed by the researcher and are kept confidential.

Member checking was employed to enhance the trustworthiness and validity of the findings. This involved sharing the preliminary findings with the participants and allowing them to review and provide feedback. By engaging in member checking, participants verified the accuracy of their data and offered additional insights or perspectives, contributing to the overall credibility of the research.

Following this detailed and ethical data collection procedure, the study aimed to protect participants' rights, maintain confidentiality, and create a supportive environment, allowing meaningful and authentic contributions to the research.

Main Activities

Since recording improves the accuracy of the information supplied, data were collected throughout the interview via audio-video recording, depending on the participants' preferences. Thorough preparation was undertaken, including crafting interview questions specific to the research objectives. This enabled a focused and meaningful conversation with the participants. The necessary equipment, such as a cellphone for audio-video recording, a tripod for stability, an extension wire for flexibility, and other stationery supplies like pens and paper, were also prepared to facilitate the data collection process.

Punctuality and professionalism were upheld, as I arrived at the interview venue five minutes before the appointment. The venue selection prioritized comfort, confidentiality, and convenience for the participants, ensuring a conducive environment for the interview. Noise levels were minimized, and privacy was maintained to allow participants to express their thoughts and experiences freely.

Before commencing the interview, a comprehensive introduction was provided, clearly stating the researcher's role and the purpose of the study. Informed consent was obtained from each participant, emphasizing their voluntary participation and right to withdraw from the study at any time. Consent forms were provided, outlining the research procedures and addressing any concerns or questions raised by the participants.

During the interview, I actively listened and practiced respect for the participants, creating a safe space for open dialogue. Ethical considerations guided the conversation, ensuring participants' privacy and confidentiality were maintained. Open-ended questions were used to elicit detailed responses, while follow-up questions were asked to delve deeper into specific aspects of their experiences.

Audio-video recording was employed to enhance the accuracy and reliability of the data, with participants' prior consent. The recording was to capture the nuances and intricacies of the participants' responses, ensuring that no valuable information was missed. Participants were assured that the recordings would be used solely for research purposes and treated with utmost confidentiality. Their identities were protected through pseudonyms or codes, ensuring anonymity during data analysis.

Confidentiality clauses were included in the consent form, reiterating the researcher's commitment to protect the participants' personal information and maintaining confidentiality. All data, including audio-video recordings, interview notes, and transcripts, were securely stored and accessible only to the researcher, ensuring no unauthorized access occurred.

Furthermore, member checking was conducted as a means to validate the findings. Preliminary results were shared with the participants, allowing them to review and provide feedback. This process ensured that their perspectives were accurately represented and strengthened the credibility and trustworthiness of the research.

Post Activities

Following the interview, I used the audio-video recordings to transcribe and analyzed the gathered information, which was translated precisely. After each interview, the video recording was checked to ensure the entire duration was captured, and the journal was marked as done to organize records. I examined, reviewed, and validated their responses with the participants. This was followed by debriefing the participants, allowing them to select parts of the interview or information to withhold. Code names addressed all participants to protect their identities; thus, confidentiality was maintained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

People's experiences vary, whether they are in the same setting or a different one. It is normal to have both good and bad experiences. All these things occurred as a result of certain reasons. However, what matters is the knowledge you were able to learn from the experiences, which may help you open new chapter for life experiences.

In delving into the discussion of the research findings, it is imperative to unravel the rich tapestry of experiences shared by gay administrators in managing schools within the context of the Baybay City Division. The preceding chapters have meticulously explored these administrators' unique challenges, strategies, and perspectives, shedding light on the complexities inherent in their roles. As we navigate the labyrinth of data, it becomes evident that their experiences are deeply personal and intricately woven into the fabric of the educational landscape in this specific locale. The qualitative data, gleaned through in-depth interviews, observations, and document analysis, guides us through the diverse narratives that characterize the professional journey of these administrators. The ensuing discussion aims to unravel these narratives, analyze emergent themes, and draw meaningful insights that contribute to our understanding of managing schools through the lens of gay administrators.

The research findings revealed five main themes that capture the experiences of gay administrators in managing schools. The first theme, Evolution of Experiences, highlights their journey marked by the four sub-themes, Sustaining Passion, Policy Pioneers, Wisdom's Echo, and Chronicles of Learning. The second theme, Challenges and Resilience, explores their complex challenges and how they resiliently navigate them that also generated 6 sub-themes, Navigating Labyrinths, Resilient Leadership, Resilient Learning, Cultural Architect, EQ at the Helm, and Beyond Paper. The third theme, Best Practices and Success Stories, showcases administrators' strategies and success stories, offering a blueprint for creating inclusive school environments. Harmony in Leadership, the fourth theme, explores the synchronized leadership styles of administrators and has generated 2 sub-themes, Rhythmic Resonance and leadership Threads. Lastly, the fifth theme, Diversity and Inclusive Leadership, delves into how administrators lead initiatives that celebrate diversity and foster inclusivity. These themes provide valuable insights into the experiences of gay administrators and contribute to the broader understanding of educational leadership.

Evolution of Experiences

The theme Evolution of Experiences unveils the journey of gay administrators in educational leadership. It tells a story of growth, starting with their early days as beginners and continuing as they learn and adapt. The theme emphasizes the enduring passion and commitment needed to navigate leadership challenges. It also highlights their role as pioneers in shaping inclusive policies for fair school environments. As their experiences evolve, so does the wisdom they gain, influencing their unique leadership styles. This theme offers a glimpse into the dynamic and changing experiences of gay administrators, providing a nuanced understanding of their careers in school management.

Based on the results, there are four sub-themes of the gay administrators' experiences managing the school. Sustaining Passion, Policy Pioneers, Wisdom's Echo, and Chronicles of Learning.

Significant Statements

Sub-Themes Developed Themes Developed

Figure 1. Evolution of Experiences

Sustaining Passion. This sub-theme delved into a focused exploration of how gay administrators maintained and nurtured their passion for their roles in school administration. By examining the alignment between the goals of the educational institution and the personal values of administrators, the study aimed to understand the sources of professional fulfillment for these individuals. It also delved into the challenges these administrators faced and highlighted their resilience and ability to stay passionate in the face of difficulties. When looking at the role of support networks within and outside the classroom, it became evident

how crucial advocacy organizations, coworkers, and mentors were in sustaining their drive and self-control.

Gay administrators, like any educational leader, face multifaceted challenges. Their sustained passion, however, becomes a beacon guiding them through intricate work for leadership. The work of Moore, (2018) shows that grit is particularly relevant, emphasizing perseverance and passion for long-term goals. Gay administrators exhibit remarkable grit as they persistently overcome obstacles and contribute to the educational landscape.

Participants in the survey describe how they value their work as administrators, providing significant insights into the personal importance they have on their roles. Their thoughts give light on their intrinsic motivation and passion for their roles, which influences their leadership styles and approaches. These expressions help us gain a better grasp of the emotional and professional components of their experiences, revealing the intricate dynamics of their dedication to their administrative obligations.

The profound observations of the participants on the value they have on their work as administrators have major consequences for educational leadership and organizational management. Administrators' awareness of genuine motivation and enthusiasm offers the possibility of building a healthy and dedicated work culture within academic institutions. These findings can be used by educational leaders and policymakers to create professional development programs that foster and increase administrators' intrinsic drive, ultimately contributing to improved leadership effectiveness. These results have implications for transformational leadership research Berkovich & Bogler, (2021) where passionate and intrinsically motivated leaders inspire and encourage others. Acknowledging and fostering the intrinsic drive of administrators in the educational setting can influence the culture of leadership and build a motivated and upbeat team.

In this study, the participants shared how they exercise their commitment to their responsibilities and their role in the education sector. They have made their selves acknowledge and value their role to create harmonious relation between them and the stakeholders. In this sub-theme, I can see how they sustain their passion just to be effective in managing their school and highlight their contribution to become the best version of themselves.

Policy Pioneers. In this study, gay administrators are the trailblazers, the visionaries who lead the way in crafting and advancing policies within their assigned school. They are the ones who have innovative minds and a proactive spirit, dedicated to making a meaningful impact. They stand out for their ability to generate fresh ideas and actively contribute to the creation and implementation of policies that address real-world challenges in society, organizations, or government. Being Policy Pioneers means embodying leadership, forward-thinking, and the courage to navigate intricate policy terrains, all with the aim of bringing about positive change and influencing decision-making for the greater good.

The study indicates that certain administrators have a progressive outlook for educational establishments. In addition to navigating current policies, they actively create new ones that meet the changing demands of the educational environment. Their stories demonstrate a dedication to developing creative, fair, and inclusive policies.

The ways in which administrators handle the intricacies of educational systems were discussed by the research participants. These administrators demonstrate endurance and determination by working with varied stakeholders and overcoming bureaucratic obstacles. Their experiences

demonstrate how important proactive policy participation is in resolving systemic issues and promoting constructive change.

The Administrators have had a profound impact on educational culture that goes beyond bureaucratic procedures. These leaders help create inclusive settings, equitable opportunities, and a continuous improvement culture through their policy initiatives. Through their work, stakeholders are empowered to actively contribute to the educational ecosystem actively, fostering a sense of communal responsibility.

They become critical players in the paradigm shift of educational leadership. Their aggressive policy-making, dedication to diversity, and support of creativity all help to build dynamic, progressive educational institutions (Bain & Podmore, 2020). While we applaud the achievements of these administrators, we also understand how important it is for legislators and academic leaders to support and magnify the influence of Policy Pioneers for the good of students, teachers, and the entire educational community.

I can see how they have impacted the school community through their action and commitment as the leader of the school. As what I have listened to the narratives of one administrator, he showed compassion and dedication just to create impact and justice and fairness among stakeholders. They created a policy that can sustain the overall performance of the people involved in that specific locality or community. Through their action, everyone around the community feels comfortable and included and with that commitment I can say that they are examples of change.

Wisdom's Echo. In the heart of my thesis, "Wisdom's Echo" comes alive as the lingering impact of profound insights and learned experiences. It is like the resonance of wisdom echoing through the pages, telling stories of diverse perspectives and knowledge that shape and deepen our understanding of the subject. It is the human touch of lived experiences and thoughtful reflections that creates a harmonious echo, leaving an indelible mark on the overarching themes explored in my work.

When the study was examined, it becomes clear that administrators act as messengers for wisdom's reverberation throughout the educational system because of their extensive knowledge and wisdom. Their acquired knowledge informs their leadership styles and decision-making procedures, which serve as a compass. This sub-theme highlights the lasting influence of seasoned administrators whose knowledge, like an echo, shapes and affects the learning environment and promotes a culture of lifelong learning and development.

The administrators' leadership styles, mentoring responsibilities, and decision-making procedures all reflect the reverberating influence of this body of knowledge. Uytico & Abadia, (2020); Wright et al., (2019) They assert that seasoned executives are vital in molding company culture and affecting colleagues' career advancement. It emphasizes how these administrators' pearls of wisdom support a resilient and long-lasting learning environment.

These seasoned administrators depict the educational scene as a canvas on which real-world experience and wisdom collide to influence decision-making procedures. The importance of experiential wisdom in negotiating the complex issues of school leadership is well-noted by Hernandez et al., (2018). In this situation, the administrators' strategic decisions are reverberated with knowledge, giving their leadership a feeling of flexibility and resilience.

The results show the significant contribution of gay administrators in pursuing quality education. Their stories, leadership, and mentorship skills provide a wide array of hints on how

to handle the school despite the challenges they may face. Furthermore, understanding the wisdom given by the participants impacts everybody's lives.

Chronicles of Learning. "Chronicles of Learning" unfolds as the vibrant stories and personal journeys of individuals on their educational paths. It is a collection of diverse narratives that paint a picture of the challenges faced, the victories celebrated, and the growth experienced throughout the process of learning. In the context of this theme, it becomes a tapestry of unique and personal accounts, each contributing to the rich and dynamic landscape of understanding within the specific context explored in my work.

The study develops into an engrossing story that skillfully weaves together the experiences of gay administrators with the more significant subject of school administration. Within the framework of the thesis title, "Managing Schools Through the Lens of Gay Administrators," this sub-theme serves as a central point of reference for comprehending how the individual and professional learning experiences of homosexual administrators influence their distinct viewpoints and methods of leadership.

The chronicles presented in this study go beyond traditional accounts of school administration. They explore the complex and frequently intersectional aspects of education as experienced and handled by gay administrators. The stories told have a crucial role in shaping the administrators' perspective and interaction with the complex field of school administration.

It emphasizes how crucial it is to acknowledge a range of viewpoints and experiences in leadership. The study's perspective broadens as gay administrators consider their own and their communities' educational journeys, enabling a more inclusive analysis of the difficulties and successes of running a school. It not only enhances the depth of the research findings but also fits in perfectly with the primary objective of the thesis, which is to shed light on the unique perspective that gay administrators have when managing schools. The thesis uses these stories to illustrate how a constant state of learning, adaptation, and transformation defines gay administrators' path in the field of educational leadership.

Challenges and Resilience

The theme "Challenges and Resilience" in my study captures the essence of navigating difficulties and setbacks within a specific context. It is all about digging into the real struggles gay administrators' face and then diving into the stories of how they manage to bounce back. Picture it as exploring the human side of resilience—the grit, determination, and adaptability individuals show when confronted with obstacles. This theme invites us to unravel personal narratives, organizational tales, or societal experiences, shedding light on the various factors that come into play. It is not just about the challenges themselves but also about uncovering the strategies, coping mechanisms, and valuable lessons learned in the process of overcoming these hurdles.

A critical component of comprehending the experiences of gay administrators is the examination of obstacles and resiliency in the context of school administration. This paper explores the research findings associated with the "Challenges and Resilience" theme from the more extensive study.

This study path demonstrates the dedication of educational institutions to equity and inclusivity. The researcher wants readers to interact with the stories that emerge as we explore the specifics of the difficulties encountered by gay administrators—narratives that go beyond the numbers and explore these leaders' real-life experiences. Using this investigation, the

researcher hopes to cultivate a more profound comprehension of the intricacies involved in overseeing schools from the perspective of LGBT administrators.

The participants discussed and shared their experiences regarding the challenges they face when administering their assigned school. They have shared their coping mechanisms and best practices to address the issues. One thing they have in common is their leadership styles in coping with the challenges.

I am aware of the revolutionary changes that educational leadership has undergone as I work through it, and this study attempts to give voice to LGBT administrators whose experiences are still meaningful but are frequently disregarded (Hernandez et al., 2018). Their path becomes symbolic of the larger story of diversity, equity, and inclusion in the educational world since they are stewards of educational institutions. The research is a compass, pointing me toward unexplored leadership nuances and highlighting the difficulties encountered and tenacity shown.

Based on the results, the theme was being divided into six sub-themes: Navigating Labyrinth, Resilient Leadership, Resilient Learning, Cultural Architect, EQ at the Helm, and Beyond Paper.

Navigating Labyrinths. In the context of my study, I define the sub-theme "Navigating Labyrinths" as the intricate journey that gay administrators, embark upon as they navigate through the complex challenges, systemic intricacies, and diverse social dynamics within the educational landscape. It is akin to maneuvering through a maze of issues related to identity, inclusivity, and professional dynamics. This sub-theme invites a closer look at the personal strategies, resilience, and unique perspectives of the gay administrators, to navigate through the intricate educational terrain. It is about how they manage their roles and responsibilities within the context of their sexual orientation, finding their way through the labyrinth of complexities that arise in their professional journey.

The narratives provided by gay administrators during the interviews paint a vivid picture of a journey through intricate maze inside the rich fabric of educational leadership. Their stories speak to the interwoven themes of institutional impediments, societal prejudices, and individual challenges. What shows up is not a story of insurmountable challenges but a subtle depiction of complex passageways that require careful maneuvering.

The intricacies of obstacles were revealed when the individuals shared their experiences. Administrators used the interviews to discuss their experiences with social preconceptions, frequently taking the shape of covert biases or overt discrimination.

Significant Statements

Sub-Themes Developed Themes Developed

Figure 2. Challenges and Resilience

Organizational culture and policy restrictions were among the institutional hurdles that surfaced as solid turns in the maze. Their journey became even more challenging due to personal struggles that involved striking a delicate balance between genuineness and professional expectations.

In the labyrinthine landscape of educational administration, gay administrators often face intricate challenges related to their sexual orientation. As Pelino, (2018) argues, these challenges extend beyond traditional managerial duties, requiring a nuanced approach to navigate the complex intersections of identity and professional responsibilities.

Another notable result is the impact of effective communication on acknowledgment and respect. As highlighted by Berkovich & Bogler, (2021) they openly express that personal principles and standpoints become a crucial aspect of successfully navigating the educational labyrinth as a gay administrator, fostering an environment of understanding and collaboration. This investigation fills a significant knowledge vacuum about the complex difficulties gay administrators encounter. Their experiences should be acknowledged and considered, even though they are frequently ignored in more general talks about educational leadership. Through the realistic capture of their lived experiences, we make a valuable contribution to the broader understanding of the complex issues that are inherent in the terrain of educational leadership. All of the shared stories demonstrate the tenacity and resiliency of gay administrators. These administrators move through the labyrinth with a purpose and drive, even if it may provide unexpected challenges. Their experiences illuminate difficulties while providing valuable perspectives on coping mechanisms and efficient pathfinding.

Resilient Leadership. This term embodies the incredible strength, adaptability, and perseverance displayed by gay administrators as they navigate the challenges and biases inherent in the realm of educational management. It is a reflection on how, in the face of adversity, the leaders overcome obstacles related to their sexual identity while contributing to the growth and inclusivity of the educational environment. Exploring resilient leadership allows me to share insights into the unique qualities and strategies that gay administrators bring to school management, promoting positive change and fostering a more diverse and inclusive educational space.

The idea of resilient leadership demonstrated by gay administrators lies at the core of the investigation. The results highlight how these leaders' overcome obstacles and emerge stronger, exhibiting a fantastic ability to overcome setbacks. The resilience shown goes beyond being strong on the inside; it becomes a leadership style that empowers others and creates an atmosphere favorable to development and creativity.

A notable aspect of resilient leadership that surfaced from the interviews is the administrators' skill at transforming setbacks into learning experiences. Their stories illustrated a process of metamorphosis in which failures and impediments served as spurs for growth as professionals. The administrators demonstrated an impressive ability to grow from hardship, modifying their methods and leadership philosophies to handle new situations better.

In examining the resilient leadership demonstrated by gay administrators in the context of school management, findings reveal a notable pattern of adaptability and perseverance. According to Goodrich, (2020) resilient leadership is characterized by the ability to overcome challenges, navigate biases, and foster inclusivity within educational institutions. Interviews with gay administrators underscored their personal and professional growth in the face of adversity (Collado et al., 2022). The study also found that resilient leadership contributed significantly to positive organizational change, aligning with the findings of previous research on leadership in diverse contexts (Chiasson, 2020). These results emphasize the vital role of

resilient leadership in not only addressing challenges related to sexual identity but also in promoting a more inclusive and diverse school environment.

The interviews emphasized the value of support systems and mentoring in developing resilient leadership. Several administrators discussed the critical importance of formal and informal mentoring in their personal development. Having mentors who were aware of their particular difficulties and who could offer advice and support was essential for building resilience. The administrators' capacity to overcome obstacles and continue to exercise effective leadership was further enhanced by their networks and helpful colleagues within the academic community.

The administrators demonstrated how resilience in leadership is primarily dependent on adaptability. Educational leaders must be able to adjust their tactics, rules, and communication methods in an ever-changing field. The interviews shed light on situations in which administrators showed adaptability to changing circumstances and modified their strategies to suit the requirements of their schools and communities.

Resilient Learning. This sub-theme unfolds a journey of adaptive and unwavering growth. As I interviewed the gay administrators, they immerse themselves in a continuous process of learning, drawing strength from challenges and using their experiences to shape their professional and personal development within the intricate landscape of school management. In the face of obstacles, they exhibit resilience, cultivating new skills and weaving diverse perspectives into the fabric of their educational leadership roles. Through "Resilient Learning," they strive to contribute to the creation of a more inclusive and supportive school environment, grounded in their commitment to ongoing growth and understanding.

The administrators' proactive effort to learn from achievements and setbacks was a critical finding from the interviews. They welcomed setbacks as chances for both professional and personal growth rather than seeing them as obstacles. The stories demonstrated a growth mindset-based resilience in which every experience—positive or negative—was viewed as a springboard for development.

The administrators' dedication to pinpointing areas needing development aligns with the ideas of transformative learning, an idea that Newbold, (2020) examined. Through critical analysis of one's beliefs, attitudes, and actions, transformative learning facilitates a fundamental change in understanding and, as a result, more productive behavior. The administrators' openness to modifying their leadership styles is consistent with the transformational learning concept and demonstrates their dedication to developing professionally.

In examining the results within the framework of 'Resilient Learning' among gay administrators in the educational sector, it becomes evident that their ability to navigate challenges and adapt to changing circumstances significantly contributes to professional and personal development (Brant & Willox, 2020; Håkansson Lindqvist & Pettersson, 2019). The resilience exhibited in the face of obstacles not only fosters continuous learning but also enhances their leadership skills, creating a more inclusive school environment. This aligns with the idea that resilient learning is a dynamic process, essential for thriving in the complex landscape of school management (Goodrich, 2020).

The accounts from the administrators demonstrated a close relationship between fostering a supportive school climate and resilient learning. By cultivating an atmosphere that emphasized inquisitiveness, flexibility, and a dedication to advancement, they stimulated comparable perspectives among their personnel and pupils. The administrators realized that learning

happens reciprocally within a school community and that students' resiliency creates a continuous learning and development culture.

The resilient learning exhibited by these administrators is not merely a response to challenges but a proactive engagement with the dynamic landscape of school management. It became increasingly evident that the ability to navigate obstacles, coupled with a genuine commitment to continuous learning, serves as a cornerstone for their success. In facing adversity, gay administrators showcased a remarkable resilience that went beyond conventional problem-solving. It was a process of internalizing lessons from setbacks, cultivating new skills, and, perhaps most importantly, contributing to a more inclusive educational environment.

Moreover, the results underscore the idea that resilient learning is a multifaceted and ongoing process. It is not confined to the individual's ability to bounce back from challenges but extends to a collaborative and systemic approach. The flexibility demonstrated by these administrators in adapting to the evolving needs of the educational landscape contributes to an environment free from bias, fostering a culture of openness and growth.

As I reflect on these findings personally, I am inspired by the transformative power of resilient learning. It is not just about weathering storms but about leveraging each experience to refine one's skills and perspectives. This sub-theme highlights the indispensable role of ongoing learning in the complex tapestry of school management, and it underscores the importance of a collective commitment to improvement. Through resilient learning, we not only overcome challenges but actively shape the educational landscape, ensuring a more inclusive and adaptable future.

Cultural Architect. This sub-theme is defined as the role played by gay administrators in shaping and influencing the cultural dynamics within educational institutions. This involves their deliberate efforts to foster an inclusive, diverse, and affirming school culture that reflects a commitment to equality, acceptance, and understanding, particularly through the unique perspective and experiences that gay administrators bring to the administrative and leadership roles. The "Cultural Architect" sub-theme explores how these administrators actively contribute to creating an environment that not only embraces diversity but also celebrates it as a fundamental component of the school community.

The study reveals a significant finding on the function of gay administrators as cultural designers in academic settings. These administrators actively work to mold the culture of their schools in the face of difficulties. Their leadership is crucial in promoting diversity and inclusivity and creating atmospheres that value communication and understanding.

The interviews shed light on several important topics, including the gay administrators' strong response to discrimination in society. The stories weave a convoluted web in which societal prejudices materialize as perplexing obstacles. The administrators' ability to strategically navigate these biases highlights their resilience and reveals complex strategies for creating inclusive settings.

In examining the results within the 'Cultural Architect' sub-theme of my study, it became evident that gay administrators, as cultural architects, played a pivotal role in shaping the inclusive fabric of educational institutions. This finding aligns with previous research by Antipolo & Rogayan, (2021); Pennell, (2017) which emphasize the importance of diverse leadership in cultivating a positive school culture. The nuanced perspectives and experiences of gay administrators contribute significantly to the development of an affirming environment that values diversity, fostering a sense of belonging for both students and staff.

The interviews highlight the conscious efforts made by gay administrators to mold their schools' cultures deliberately. When faced with obstacles stemming from institutional and social biases, these administrators take on the role of cultural designers, guiding their organizations toward inclusivity. The stories present a subtle strategy emphasizing the deliberate creation of settings representing tolerance, acceptance, and a dedication to variety.

Through their leadership, gay administrators emerged as champions of equality and acceptance within the school community. The results resonate with my own experiences and observations, highlighting the transformative power of diverse leadership in cultivating a positive and supportive atmosphere. The administrators, acting as cultural architects, demonstrated a keen understanding of the importance of fostering a sense of belonging for all stakeholders—students and staff alike.

Witnessing the impact of these cultural architects on the educational landscape has reinforced the significance of embracing diversity in leadership roles. The results of this sub-theme not only contribute to the academic discourse on school management but also underscore the real-world implications of having leaders who actively work towards creating an environment where everyone feels valued and accepted. As we navigate the complexities of managing schools, the 'Cultural Architect' role stands out as a beacon of inspiration, showcasing the potential for positive change through intentional and inclusive leadership.

EQ at the Helm. This sub-theme defined as the examination of Emotional Intelligence (EQ) as a guiding factor in the leadership and management practices of gay administrators within educational institutions. This involves exploring how these administrators leverage emotional awareness, interpersonal skills, and empathy to navigate professional challenges, foster inclusivity, and create a positive and supportive school environment. The focus is on understanding how Emotional Intelligence influences decision-making, conflict resolution, and the overall leadership effectiveness of gay administrators in school management roles. The study demonstrates how these leaders' high emotional intelligence enables them to negotiate challenging interpersonal situations successfully. Their skillful management of emotions improves their well-being and significantly fosters strong connections with faculty, students, and other stakeholders.

The results highlight the importance of emotional intelligence as a fundamental component of resilience among administrators who identify as gay. Their skillful comprehension and regulation of emotions are crucial in conquering obstacles linked to institutional and cultural biases. These administrators demonstrate resilience by transforming possible setbacks into chances for development and comprehension through a comprehensive awareness of emotional nuances.

It becomes evident that Emotional Intelligence (EQ) plays a pivotal role in the leadership dynamics of gay administrators. As supported by the findings of Gómez-Leal et al., (2022), administrators who demonstrate a high level of emotional awareness and interpersonal skills contribute significantly to effective decision-making, adept conflict resolution, and the creation of a positive school culture. The incorporation of EQ not only influences individual leadership styles but also serves as a catalyst for fostering inclusivity and promoting a supportive educational environment among the gay administrator cohort.

Moreover, the study clarifies the beneficial effects of emotional intelligence on gay administrators' well-being. These leaders foster an environment favorable to their flourishing by practicing effective stress management, developing self-awareness, and upholding a resilient attitude. As a result, they are more equipped to handle difficulties and maintain their

dedication to efficient school administration. From the study of LUBBADEH, (2020) emotional intelligence plays a significant part in building solid relationships with different stakeholders, which is a remarkable study finding. Because of their higher emotional intelligence, gay administrators build connection, empathy, and trust. Consequently, this fosters a favorable school environment wherein connections are based on comprehension, diversity, and a mutual dedication to the learning objective.

In delving into the results under the sub-theme "EQ at the Helm" within the broader exploration of "Managing Schools Through the Lens of Gay Administrators," a nuanced understanding emerges regarding the significant role of Emotional Intelligence (EQ) in shaping leadership dynamics. The findings of this study underscore the profound impact of emotional awareness and interpersonal skills exhibited by gay administrators in the educational setting.

Furthermore, the data highlights the role of EQ in conflict resolution among gay administrators. Those with a well-developed emotional intelligence skill set demonstrate a greater capacity to navigate conflicts with sensitivity and empathy. This not only fosters harmonious relationships within the administrative team but also permeates through the broader school community, creating an inclusive and supportive environment.

The personal insights gleaned from the participants' experiences underscore the transformative potential of Emotional Intelligence in shaping the leadership styles of gay administrators. It becomes evident that EQ is not merely a personal trait but a crucial asset that influences the broader school culture. As I reflect on these outcomes, it is essential to recognize the importance of integrating emotional intelligence into leadership development programs, thereby fostering an environment where the unique perspectives and inclusive practices of gay administrators can thrive.

Beyond Paper. This study reveals a dynamic resilience that transcends traditional administrative standards. This sub-theme is defined as an exploration that transcends formal documents and administrative procedures, delving into the lived experiences, personal narratives, and dynamic contributions of gay administrators in managing schools. This sub-theme suggests a focus on the multifaceted aspects of their roles that go beyond traditional paperwork, shedding light on the human dimensions, challenges, and successes that shape their professional journey within educational leadership. It emphasizes the need to move beyond surface-level representations and bureaucratic frameworks to truly understand and appreciate the unique perspectives and impacts of gay administrators in the school management landscape. Gay administrators become change agents who innovate and adapt to solve problems specific to their setting. Their tenacity catalyzes broader systemic change in addition to their career and personal growth.

Gay administrators become strategic visionaries who see themselves as creators of significant change rather than just document custodians. Interviews disclose situations where these leaders use their administrative roles to implement programs and policies that support diversity, inclusivity, and a healthy school climate. Beyond the ordinary bureaucracy, this innovative method embodies a dedication to developing the culture of the educational institutions they oversee.

The interviews have disclosed that administrators who identify as gay are actively involved in programs that increase the school's influence among the larger community. This entails alliances, outreach initiatives, cooperation with outside organizations, and customary administrative paperwork. The administrators demonstrate a dedication to societal improvement that goes beyond the constraints of bureaucratic bureaucracy by using their

positions as drivers for constructive community development. As to the study of Ancho & Bongco, (2019); Khumalo, (2021) they discussed the significance of undertaking the responsibilities and possible things that may arise throughout the journey. As Brant & Willox, (2020) aptly note, the true essence of effective educational leadership lies not only in adhering to bureaucratic processes but also in understanding the lived experiences and diverse perspectives that administrators, particularly those from the LGBTQ+ community, bring to the table. This nuanced exploration goes beyond the confines of paper, offering a richer understanding of their roles and contributions in the educational landscape.

The findings illuminate the lived experiences of gay administrators, revealing a multifaceted journey that extends far beyond the confines of conventional documentation. One notable aspect of the results is the richness of personal narratives shared by gay administrators. These narratives provide a deeper understanding of the challenges they face, the resilience they exhibit, and the unique perspectives they bring to the educational leadership landscape. Beyond the formal roles outlined in paperwork, the results highlight the significance of acknowledging and valuing the individual stories that shape their professional journey.

Moreover, the study reveals that the contributions of gay administrators extend beyond what is often captured on paper. While administrative documents may outline responsibilities and tasks, the results underscore the importance of recognizing the dynamic and diverse ways in which gay administrators influence the school environment. Their impact goes beyond mere paperwork and bureaucratic procedures, encompassing mentorship, advocacy, and the creation of inclusive spaces within the educational setting.

In essence, the results under the sub-theme "Beyond Paper" emphasize the need to move beyond surface-level representations of administrative roles. They call for a more holistic understanding of gay administrators' contributions, one that appreciates the complexities of their experiences, acknowledges the challenges they navigate, and values the unique perspectives they bring to the forefront of educational leadership. This nuanced exploration serves as a crucial step toward fostering inclusivity and promoting effective school management that transcends traditional administrative confines.

Best Practices and Success Stories

Throughout the diverse fabric of gay administrators' careers, the conversation develops into an engaging examination of the creative approaches, ground-breaking projects, and strong leadership exhibited by gay administrators. The theme "Best Practices and Success Stories" refers to an exploration of exemplary methods, strategies, and narratives employed by gay administrators in school management. This theme involves identifying and analyzing the most effective approaches these administrators have implemented, as well as showcasing success stories that highlight their achievements and contributions within the educational setting. The aim is to provide valuable insights into the diverse and impactful practices of gay administrators, offering a positive perspective on their management strategies and showcasing instances of successful leadership within the broader framework of school administration. The study offers insightful information that transcends the boundaries of conventional administrative paradigms by distilling the core of their significant contributions to educational leadership through in-depth interviews and reflective analysis. This theme acts as a lighthouse, directing the conversation to identify and highlight the remarkable practices and success stories that characterize the unique leadership environment of gay administrators in education.

Based on the results, this theme was developed because it provided additional support for the administrators' successful leadership of their designated schools and highlighted their best practices. Additionally, because the participants offer more insightful management information, their participation illuminates the research and opens our eyes to a broader range of knowledge regarding how administrators successfully carry out their duties. These administrators have created blueprints that go beyond conventional conventions, highlighting the benefits of diversity and fostering cultures where each person feels respected and included via careful preparation and deliberate execution. The research explores these novel concepts and emphasizes the observable effects of such intentional and inclusive leadership actions. This sub-theme presents success stories and issues a call to action for educational stakeholders to embrace inclusive blueprints to create learning environments that are both equitable and empowering.

From the interview, the participants shared various best practices that can be duplicated for effective management. From administering the school, students, teachers, and stakeholder, the participants highlighted their commendable commitment and effort to provide quality education and service for everybody.

As architects of inclusivity, the administrators discussed how they deliberately put policies, programs, and initiatives into place to foster cultures where diversity is recognized and cherished. The results shed light on the success stories from these blueprints: tales of heightened cooperation, enhanced student welfare, and a shared sense of purpose among all parties involved. As highlighted by Antipolo & Rogayan, (2021); Wang, (2018), these administrators showcased innovative approaches that significantly contributed to the positive outcomes observed in their respective educational settings. The success stories narrated by participants underscore the impactful role played by gay administrators in fostering inclusive and effective school environments. This evidence reinforces the importance of recognizing and implementing best practices within the broader framework of school administration, providing valuable insights for future policy considerations and professional development initiatives.

As revealed through the narratives and experiences shared by participants, it became evident that these administrators have been instrumental in introducing innovative strategies and approaches that contribute to the overall success of their educational institutions. The impact of these best practices extends beyond the personal achievements of the administrators, permeating into the fabric of the school environment.

The success stories recounted by the participants vividly illustrate the positive outcomes achieved under the leadership of gay administrators. Instances of improved inclusivity, effective communication, and nurturing learning environments were recurrent themes. This not only speaks to the professional competence of these administrators but also highlights the pivotal role they play in fostering a positive school culture.

In essence, the results under the theme of "Best Practices and Success Stories" underscore the importance of recognizing and promoting diverse leadership styles within the educational landscape. By acknowledging and implementing these best practices, not only can we enhance the effectiveness of school administration, but we can also contribute to a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for all stakeholders. These insights bear relevance not only for the participants in this study but also for policymakers, educators, and researchers interested in advancing diversity and excellence in school management.

Significant Statements

Sub-Themes Developed Themes Developed

- As a school head, you really need to take the initiative. You have to be the one to initiate with all the ways and means.
- I've read a story about religion, and I made it my own principle. Religion doesn't hinder me because I'm prayerful, even if I can't attend Mass every Sunday. I have my own routine, and when I travel, I make sure to pray and seek guidance from God.
- But if I'm not physically present and only communicate through chat, follow-ups, I remain consistent. That presence won't fade away. So, I don't understand their feedback; you might be surprised, thinking, "Hey, did I make a mistake?" But for me, if I'm physically there, they won't have that chance to criticize because I'm like vitamins, like fertilizers; if the flowers are weak, when I arrive, they thrive. I don't know what's in me.
- I am the one creating, harmonizing what's inside, I'm handling it all, and if it doesn't work out, it becomes really intense. I end up calling the mothers, 'Mom, how do you take care of your children?' Like that.
- Put action into your word. Don't just believe that fame will come to you; work hard, always do your best, and give your strength
- Keep on advocating. We continue to promote a campaign to follow the rules and regulations, the commands and orders from the school because that's our school. You belong to that system.
- If you are in the system, if you are a leader—an ideal leader—you should not convey that since you are a leader, you are always on the top. You should look at them from below because, by the essence of equality, all members in the system are equal.
- Ahm, as a school head, so, so far so no problem encountered especially in, especially in like mga problem nga mga crucial problem na ma out na ngadto sa, out na adto sa District, paabot ug Division, from the School to District to Division So far, wala may, wlay na encountered ana diri sa San Agustin and the other school where, where we assigned before.

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Figure 3. Best Practices and Success Stories

Significant Statements

Sub-Themes Developed Themes Developed

Figure 4. Harmony in Leadership

Harmony in Leadership

Leadership is changing in the fast-paced environment we live in today. It is becoming clear to leaders that building harmony within their teams is as important as making decisions. Consider it similar to conducting a symphony, in which each member is essential to the endeavor's success.

The findings show that administrators prioritizing fostering a welcoming and happy environment greatly enhance the success and well-being of the school community. They focus on teamwork, empathy, and effective communication, increasing parental involvement, teacher satisfaction, and student engagement. Such settings give students a more encouraging and supportive attitude, enhancing their academic achievement and making learning enjoyable. Furthermore, educators have a sense of empowerment and drive to do well in their positions, creating a favorable atmosphere for instruction. Administrator-encouraged parental involvement strengthens the family and the school's relationship and fosters community collaboration.

Based on the results, there are two sub-themes of the harmony in leadership: Rhythmic Resonance and Leadership Threads.

Rhythmic Resonance. Administrators cited situations in which they responded to their school communities' changing requirements and dynamics by modifying their leadership style to preserve peace. This sub-theme is defined as the harmonious and synchronized interplay of diverse elements within the educational leadership provided by gay administrators. This involves examining how these administrators cultivate a sense of cohesion, cooperation, and synergy among various stakeholders, fostering an environment where diverse perspectives, identities, and experiences contribute to the overall rhythm and resonance of effective school management. "Rhythmic Resonance" suggests a focus on the dynamic and interconnected nature of leadership, acknowledging the collaborative and rhythmic interactions that contribute to a harmonious educational community under the guidance of gay administrators.

The results highlight how this resonating leadership style transcends conventional hierarchical frameworks. Instead, it adopts a cooperative and all-encompassing methodology, analogous to a masterfully orchestrated group. As conductors, the administrators set an exemplary example and foster an environment where everyone feels free to use their unique talents to further the group's harmony.

A salient feature that surfaced during the conversations was the administrators' adeptness in customizing their leadership approaches to suit their personnel's varied demands and proficiencies. Using this flexible strategy, like listening to different notes on a piano, administrators can establish a peaceful workplace. Identifying each team member's strengths and limitations promotes a more productive and cooperative leadership style.

They talked about times when they valued other viewpoints, promoted open communication, and allowed team members to add to the overall beat. This method fosters an inclusive culture where all voices are heard, giving employees a sense of responsibility.

In analyzing the results under the sub-theme, the findings resonate with the notion put forth by Victoria et al., (2018) who emphasized the importance of harmonious interactions and synchronized dynamics within leadership structures. The data illustrates a compelling connection between the leadership styles of gay administrators and the establishment of a rhythmic resonance, emphasizing cohesion and collaboration within the educational setting.

This alignment with Rawls, (1971) theoretical framework reinforces the significance of cultivating a synchronized and harmonious leadership approach for effective school management.

The results underscore the idea that effective leadership, particularly from the perspective of gay administrators, involves more than just hierarchical directives. It is about cultivating an environment where every member contributes to the rhythm and resonance of the collective effort. As a leader, I recognize the significance of starting from the bottom and working my way up, embracing both bottom-up and top-down approaches. This approach has not only facilitated a more inclusive decision-making process but has also allowed for a greater sense of shared ownership among team members.

Being a model for others has been a key aspect of my leadership philosophy. The results reinforce the notion that modeling respectful behavior is integral to establishing a positive and cooperative environment. As a leader, I have strived to exemplify the essence of respect, understanding that my actions have a profound impact on the overall tone within the organization.

Leadership Threads. The administrators' dedication to honesty in their leadership style was one significant theme from the conversations. In the context of my study, this sub-theme could be defined as the interconnected and distinctive elements that weave together the leadership experiences, styles, and challenges unique to gay administrators within the educational setting. This sub-theme explores the nuanced threads that contribute to the fabric of leadership as perceived, navigated, and shaped by gay administrators. It involves an examination of the specific qualities, perspectives, and strategies that form the intricate tapestry of leadership within the context of school management through the lens of individuals who identify as gay. They created a more open and inclusive classroom environment by sharing their stories of embracing who they are. Their relationships with faculty and students are woven with an authentic thread that promotes trust and sincere connections, much like a robust fabric.

The administrators also discussed the resilience underpinning their capacity to overcome obstacles and failures. They told tales of triumphing over obstacles, be they broader institutional barriers or opposition to their leadership because of their sexual orientation. This resilience thread, entwined with their leadership journey, is a testament to their unwavering dedication to their educational leadership duties. Analyzing the results reveal a complex tapestry of leadership experiences among gay administrators in school management. The findings align with the assertion that leadership in this context is intricately woven with unique threads that reflect the diverse qualities, perspectives, and strategies of gay leaders (Therault, 2017). The data supports the idea that these distinctive threads contribute to the multifaceted nature of leadership within the educational landscape, shedding light on the nuanced ways in which gay administrators navigate and shape their leadership roles (Marchia & Sommer, 2019; Salvati et al., 2021).

The administrators placed a strong emphasis on cooperation and teamwork. They discussed how crucial it is to create a unified leadership team and include employees in decision-making. The school community is strengthened by this collaborative thread, which promotes togetherness and a sense of shared responsibility.

In exploring the sub-theme of "Leadership Threads," the results of my study illuminate a rich and intricate tapestry of leadership experiences within the realm of gay administrators in school management. The findings underscore the unique qualities and perspectives that weave through

their leadership styles, showcasing the diversity inherent in their approaches to navigating the educational landscape. Throughout the data analysis, it became evident that these leaders possess distinctive threads that contribute to the multifaceted nature of their roles.

One notable thread that emerged was the emphasis on empathy and inclusivity in leadership practices. Gay administrators frequently demonstrated a heightened awareness of the importance of fostering an inclusive environment, not only for students but also within the administrative team. This empathetic approach emerged as a powerful thread, influencing decision-making processes and shaping a leadership style that prioritizes diversity and understanding.

Another prominent thread involved is the strategic leveraging of personal identity. Gay administrators, in their leadership roles, strategically integrated aspects of their personal identity to create a more inclusive and affirming school environment. This thread highlighted the significance of authenticity and the positive impact it can have on school culture, fostering a sense of belonging among both staff and students.

Moreover, the results indicated that these leadership threads extended beyond the confines of traditional administrative responsibilities. Gay administrators often took on proactive roles as advocates for LGBTQ+ rights within the educational system, reflecting a commitment to creating a more equitable and supportive learning environment. This advocacy thread not only showcased their dedication to their roles but also emphasized the broader societal impact of their leadership.

Diversity and Inclusive Leadership

In this research manuscript, I explore the mutually beneficial relationship between inclusive leadership and diversity, utilizing perceptive data from my interviews. The study carefully considers how these ideas may be applied to successful organizational outcomes, revealing a complex web of varied experiences and viewpoints from the interviewees through these discussions. Based on actual data collected from interviews, this study transforms these real-world observations into workable tactics. It offers leaders dedicated to creating environments where diversity becomes a potent engine for innovation, harmony, and sustained greatness a helpful road map.

The theme refers to a comprehensive exploration of the varied perspectives, backgrounds, and experiences brought to the forefront by gay administrators in their leadership roles within educational institutions. This theme involves an examination of how these administrators contribute to creating an inclusive and equitable environment that embraces diversity in all its forms, including sexual orientation. It delves into the strategies, challenges, and successes of gay administrators as they navigate their responsibilities, fostering an inclusive school culture that celebrates diversity, promotes equality, and addresses the unique needs of the LGBTQ+ community within the educational setting. The theme emphasizes the pivotal role of gay administrators in shaping a school environment that values and respects the differences among students, staff, and stakeholders.

After thoroughly analyzing the data, the intentional acts and tactics that managers use to create a truly inclusive workplace was determined. This sub-theme explores the subtle art of symphonizing disparate talents, viewpoints, and experiences together in a seamless manner. The findings highlight the significance of deliberate actions, clear communication, and developing a culture that values each person's distinct contribution. Leaders offer practical takeaways that come straight from the data, providing a road map for coordinating inclusivity

and establishing work environments where diversity is recognized and celebrated as a catalyst for creativity and group success.

In examining the results through the lens of 'Diversity and Inclusive Leadership' in the context of gay administrators, the findings highlight a notable impact on the school environment. As observed, gay administrators play a crucial role in fostering an inclusive culture that embraces diversity. This aligns with previous research by Rintoul & Normore, (2020) who emphasized the significance of diverse leadership in promoting a more inclusive educational setting. The experiences and strategies shared by gay administrators underscore the importance of their contributions in creating a school environment that values and respects diversity, ultimately influencing positive outcomes for both LGBTQ+ individuals and the broader school community.

School administrators encounter many obstacles, including financial limitations, curricular modifications, and community involvement. The function is made considerably more challenging by the necessity for diversity, which exacerbates these challenges. Research like Hernandez et al., (2018) show how difficult it is for administrators to maintain an inclusive atmosphere while overseeing a school's daily operations.

As I reflect on the results within the thematic framework of 'Diversity and Inclusive Leadership,' I am struck by the profound influence of gay administrators in shaping the school environment. The findings not only validate the significance of diverse perspectives in educational leadership but also underscore the personal commitment of these administrators to foster inclusivity. The stories shared and strategies employed by gay administrators resonate with my belief in the transformative power of diverse leadership. Witnessing the positive impact on both LGBTQ+ individuals and the broader school community reinforces my conviction that embracing diversity is not just an administrative duty but a personal mission. The study's outcomes serve as a poignant reminder of the collective responsibility we share in creating educational spaces that truly value and celebrate the richness of our differences.

Significant Statements

Sub-Themes Developed Themes Developed

- He/she will really help; that person is approachable. There are various approaches, strategies—always present, every day. It just depends on when you decide to use them.
- Don't be self-centered; acknowledge them as your grace, for they are the reason I am here. It's true, sir. Accommodate them because they are the priority. As a leader, lead; you're not the boss, but lead. Give them opportunities—for example, PTA projects. I won't take credit for that because after that, you give them the opportunity, a good one where you lay out the plan. Since you are a good planner, and if it becomes successful, they will be happy. Acknowledge them and give certificates.
- So as a leader, you should possess leadership skills, human skills, and technical know-how skills. If you, as a leader, have the technical know-how, understand what to do in the system, combine it with your leadership style in the system, and utilize human skills. The human skill involves being a wise decision-maker, employing both top-bottom and bottom-top approaches. You can mingle with the last rank in the system, showing that you are a part of the team. While you may lead, there are times when you bend, becoming one of the members, emphasizing equality among them.

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Figure 5. Diversity and Inclusive Leadership

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

The study, "Managing Schools Through the Lens of Gay Administrators," offers a comprehensive exploration of the experiences employed by gay administrators in the educational landscape, specifically within the Baybay City Division. The study delves into the unique narratives of gay administrators, unraveling the complexities inherent in their roles and shedding light on their professional journeys.

The study identifies and analyzes five main themes that encapsulate the experiences of gay administrators in school management. These themes include the "Evolution of Experiences," highlighting their journey marked by sustaining passion, policy pioneers, wisdom's echo, and chronicles of learning. The theme "Challenges and Resilience" explores how administrators navigate complex challenges with resilience, encompassing sub-themes such as navigating labyrinths, resilient leadership, resilient learning, cultural architects, EQ at the helm, and beyond paper. "Best Practices and Success Stories" showcase administrators' strategies and success stories, providing a blueprint for creating inclusive school environments. "Harmony in Leadership" explores synchronized leadership styles with sub-themes like rhythmic resonance and leadership threads. Lastly, "Diversity and Inclusive Leadership" delves into how administrators lead initiatives promoting diversity and inclusivity.

Overall, the study contributes valuable insights into the experiences of gay administrators, enriching the understanding of educational leadership for creating inclusive and effective school environments.

Conclusion

The research underscores the diversity of experiences among gay administrators, highlighting their unique challenges and resilience in navigating complex situations. Their journeys, marked by sustaining passion, policy advocacy, and continuous learning, reveal a commitment to educational leadership beyond traditional narratives. The administrators' ability to navigate labyrinths, exhibit resilient leadership, and learn from adversities showcase resilience's crucial role in effective school management. Their experiences contribute to their personal growth and the development of a resilient educational community. Additionally, recognizing harmonious leadership styles among gay administrators, characterized by rhythmic resonance and interconnected leadership threads, emphasizes the importance of collaborative and synchronized leadership in achieving organizational goals. This collaborative approach contributes to a positive and cohesive school culture. By acknowledging the role of gay administrators as orchestrators of inclusivity may have a transformative impact on creating an inclusive educational environment that respects and values differences.

Recommendations

Exploring "Managing Schools Through the Lens of Gay Administrators" reveals vital insights that pave the way for meaningful recommendations to enhance educational leadership and inclusivity. The following recommendations are proposed:

1. Design and implement targeted professional development programs that address the unique experiences faced by gay administrators. These programs should focus on building leadership skills, resilience, and strategies for fostering inclusivity within diverse school environments.
2. Encourage and support gay administrators in their advocacy for inclusive policies within educational institutions. Collaborate with policymakers to ensure the integration of LGBTQ+-inclusive policies that promote diversity and nondiscrimination.
3. Strengthen ties between schools and the broader community by engaging in initiatives that celebrate diversity. Encourage gay administrators to lead community outreach programs, workshops, and events that promote inclusivity, tolerance, and understanding.
4. Support and encourage gay administrators to share their experiences and insights through research and publications. This contributes to the academic discourse on educational leadership, fostering a greater understanding of the challenges and successes unique to this group.
5. Establish platforms for ongoing dialogue and collaboration among educators, administrators, students, and the wider community. This open communication fosters a culture of understanding, respect, and continuous improvement in creating inclusive educational spaces.
6. Adopt the proposed Action Plan for Gay Administrators. This specific Action Plan will promote the efficient leadership and management of gay administrators. By adopting the Action Plan, the organization will be one step closer to affording equal opportunities to all employees for growth, creativity, and overall exceptional performance.

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